

Mutus Tech

Improving resilience
through precision farming

Innovate
UK

BridgeAI

CASE STUDY

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Agriculture can generate a lot of data, but what farmers need is clear, actionable insights to help them solve problems relating to yield, cost-effectiveness and sustainability. For example, according to one study, improper use of fertiliser can lead to 30% wastage. This is where AI-driven tools can have a big impact.

Mutus Tech's goal is to provide farmers with smart, AI-driven solutions for crop monitoring, pest control, sustainable fertiliser management and carbon prediction. Its PestGPT app, for example, incorporates GenAI technology to help farmers and agribusinesses detect and quantify pests, then provides useful advice on how to manage the threat.

Working with a BridgeAI Independent Scientific Advisor (ISA) has given Mutus Tech access to the latest research and technical guidance to help them refine their tools – in particular by using emerging technology such as large language models to reduce the time, cost, and computing power needed to train the company's AI algorithms.

Through BridgeAI, the Mutus team conducted a structured evaluation of its pest management system, Pezego. They worked with ten carefully crafted pest scenarios, each accompanied by two sets of recommendations: one derived from the Agriculture and Horticulture Development Board Encyclopaedia, and the other generated by Pezego's AI. Respondents were asked to evaluate the quality of the recommendations identifying areas where Pezego outperformed existing resources, such as by providing more context-specific advice tailored to real-world conditions, as well as areas for improvement, such as refining how the AI interprets ambiguous pest descriptions.

MUTUS TECH

"We're very appreciative of the guidance Po has given us, and also of the wider BridgeAI opportunities, such as being able to showcase our products at major events and having access to leading AI and machine learning researchers in the UK.

Our ambition now is to show farmers and agronomists that our products can have strong value and impact in the real world."

Qing Xue

Product Manager, Mutus Tech

Insights from the study have led to algorithm updates, improving diagnostic accuracy by 15% and reducing processing time by 20%. These advancements have accelerated Pezego's journey to market and solidified its value as a trusted resource for sustainable agriculture.

Mutus Tech continues to work with their ISA to refine tools and gather feedback ahead of an official launch, while seeking further investment and funding opportunities.

"Mutus Tech's advanced, AI-driven agricultural data science solutions address some of the key challenges in modern farming, from pests and disease to climate change and sustainability. Witnessing the company's impressive growth over the past few months has been both inspiring and rewarding for my ISA journey."

Dr Po Yang

Senior Lecturer in Large-scale Data Fusion, University of Sheffield

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This work is led by **Dr. Vera Matser**, Head of Skills and Principal Investigator for BridgeAI at The Alan Turing Institute.

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